

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Factors Influencing the Effectiveness of the Implementation of Policies for Handling Sexual Violence Against Women and Children at the Department of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, Population Control and Family Planning of Southeast Sulawesi

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 28(03), 1170-1179

Publication history: Received on 11 November 2025; revised on 15 December 2025; accepted on 18 December 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.28.3.4205>

Abstract

This study analyzes factors influencing the effectiveness of implementing policies for handling sexual violence against women and children at the Office of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning (DP3APPKB) of Southeast Sulawesi. An analytical cross-sectional design was used and conducted in December 2025, involving 99 respondents through total sampling, including internal DP3APPKB personnel, field officers/companions, cross-sector partners, and the Children's Forum. The examined variables were communication, resources, disposition (implementers' attitudes), bureaucratic structure, and patriarchal culture. Data were analyzed using univariate analysis, bivariate chi-square tests, and multivariate logistic regression, with candidate variables selected at $p < 0.25$. Logistic regression results indicated that patriarchal culture was excluded from the final model due to having the largest p-value in the initial modeling (0.088). The final model confirms that communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure significantly influence implementation effectiveness, with resources identified as the most dominant factor (largest OR).

Keywords: Bureaucratic Structure; Policy Implementation; Resources; Sexual Violence

1. Introduction

Violence against women and children is a pressing global issue, and among these forms, sexual violence is one of the most prevalent yet least reported. Globally, approximately 1 in 3 women experience physical or sexual violence in their lifetime [1], and UN Women estimates that approximately 736 million women aged 15 and over have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by intimate partners or non-partners, and prevalence can increase sharply in humanitarian situations such as conflict, displacement, or disasters. In Southeast Asia, regional figures show that approximately 29% of women have experienced violence in various forms, including sexual violence. This fact confirms that sexual violence is systemic and cross-contextual, occurring not only in intimate relationships, but also outside of partner relationships.

Gender-based violence does not always manifest in easily visible or officially recorded forms, but also manifests as psychological violence, sexual coercion, sexual harassment, exploitation, and domestic violence, often occurring in private spaces with perpetrators who have close relationships with the victims. Its impacts are broad, ranging from physical injuries and mental health disorders, unwanted pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections, to restrictions on victims' socio-economic participation. Due to its scale and diversity, addressing gender-based violence requires an

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integrated, cross-sectoral response encompassing law enforcement, social protection and recovery services, changes in socio-cultural norms, strengthening gender mainstreaming, and reliable data mechanisms to monitor interventions.

In the Indonesian context, the burden of violence against women and children remains high and fluctuating. Data from the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (Kemen PPPA) shows that throughout 2022–2024, cases of violence against women and children remained alarming, with sexual violence being the dominant form among child victims, and disparities in figures between reporting sources (e.g., SIMFONI-PPA and CATAHU). This situation indicates that prevention and protection efforts have not fully reduced the number of incidents, while under-reporting and social norms that silence victims remain major challenges [2]. At the regional level, Southeast Sulawesi Province also shows a worrying trend. The DP3APPKB reported 212 cases of sexual violence against women and children in 2022, increasing to 545 in 2023, and 585 in 2024. Furthermore, regional records also emphasize the concentration of cases in urban areas such as Kendari and Bau-Bau, as well as the need to improve the effectiveness of response services.

The Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Government has a regional policy framework, including Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Regulation Number 4 of 2018 concerning the Protection of Women and Children Victims of Violence, which emphasizes the regional government's responsibility for the prevention, protection, and recovery of victims, including strengthening service institutions such as the UPTD PPA and P2TP2A. However, policy implementation still faces significant obstacles in the form of limited trained human resources, minimal budget support, weak cross-sectoral coordination, and low public awareness and courage to report due to stigma and patriarchal culture. This vulnerability is exacerbated by socio-cultural factors. Patriarchal culture and power relations within families/communities can produce a "culture of silence," encourage resolution of sexual violence through family/customary mechanisms that are not oriented towards victim justice, and trigger re-victimization when victims are blamed. In the Kendari context, patriarchal culture and economic dependency are cited as important causal factors that hinder prevention and handling [3].

Conceptually, this issue cannot be separated from the dynamics of public policy and its implementation. Public policy can be understood as the government's choice to do or not do something [4], and is carried out through a continuous process starting from agenda setting, formulation, adoption, implementation, and evaluation [5][6]. At the implementation stage, the success of the policy is largely determined by key variables, especially communication, resources, implementer disposition, and bureaucratic structure (Edwards III). Therefore, assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of policies to address sexual violence requires an analysis of both internal factors of the implementing organization and external factors such as patriarchal culture that influence service responses and reporting participation. The need for this study is further strengthened by the existence of a research gap. It is stated that scientific studies based on in-depth and representative local data at the regional/rural level are still limited; many studies are descriptive and not sufficiently analytical or longitudinal, thus reducing the relevance of evidence-based policies (policy relevance gap). Limitations of integrated data systems and differences in reporting between regions also complicate precise policy formulation and continuous evaluation [2].

A review of previous research shows a relatively consistent pattern of implementation obstacles. Aini Janah (2021) found that the implementation of handling violence against women and children has not been optimal due to limited human resources, finances, and infrastructure, as well as community stigma that discourages reporting. Supporting factors include skilled human resources, communication between services, and intensive outreach [7]. Sutopo (2024) showed that the implementation of protection for victims of domestic violence is influenced by communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. Obstacles arise from internal differences of opinion, a lack of human resources and facilities (e.g., safe houses), and the need for clearer SOPs and boundaries of authority [8]. Yulista Sari (2022) concluded that the program for protecting and fulfilling women's rights is running quite well, but is strongly influenced by policy planning, program outputs/benefits, and implementing resources [9].

Todapa (2024) emphasized implementation barriers in the form of minimal outreach, budget constraints, and the lack of UPTDs to support services [10]. Maghfiro (2022) showed that P2TP2A services were running well but not optimally due to limited staff presence and direct outreach; other obstacles included a lack of budget and inadequate infrastructure. This is at the international level [11]. Bacchus et al. (2024) emphasized that multi-component interventions are most consistently effective, but their success is determined by structural support, sustainable funding, local leadership, service integration, and monitoring [12]. Meanwhile, Olson et al. (2020) found that the one-stop center model has the potential to increase service access, but is often hampered by weak intersectoral coordination, inadequate staff capacity, weak referral pathways, and uncertainty about operational funding [13].

Based on these overall conditions, this study is positioned to address the evaluative-analytical needs regarding the effectiveness of the implementation of policies addressing sexual violence against women and children in the

DP3APPKB of Southeast Sulawesi. The research focuses on examining the influence of communication, resources, disposition, bureaucratic structure, and patriarchal culture on the effectiveness of policy implementation. The results are expected to clarify the inhibiting/driving factors and serve as the basis for recommendations for strengthening services, coordination, human resource capacity, and strategies for changing social norms at the regional level.

2. Methods

This study uses a quantitative analytical approach with a cross-sectional design to analyze the influence of communication, resources, implementer disposition, bureaucratic structure, and patriarchal culture on the effectiveness of the implementation of policies for handling sexual violence against women and children at the DP3APPKB (Regional Disaster Management Agency) of Southeast Sulawesi Province. The study population consisted of 99 people consisting of DP3APPKB officials and cross-sector partners, and all were sampled through a total sampling technique. Data were collected using a closed-ended questionnaire based on a Likert scale that has been tested for validity and reliability so that it is suitable for use as a research instrument. Data analysis was carried out through univariate analysis, bivariate analysis with the Chi-Square test, and multivariate analysis using logistic regression to determine the most dominant factors influencing the effectiveness of policy implementation. The study was conducted in December 2025 using primary and secondary data, and processed using SPSS. The entire research process was carried out in accordance with the principles of research ethics, including respondent consent, anonymity, and data confidentiality.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework Scheme

3. Results

3.1 Overview of Research Location

This research was conducted at the Southeast Sulawesi Province Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning (DP3APPKB), an institution with a primary mandate to formulate and implement policies addressing sexual violence against women and children. The DP3APPKB oversees the Women and Children Protection Technical Implementation Unit (UPTD PPA), which serves as the frontline in providing victim services, including complaint services, legal and psychological assistance, and cross-sectoral coordination.

3.2 Respondent Characteristics

Table 1 Respondent Characteristics Based on Age

No.	Age (Years)	n	%
1	20 - 29 Years	30	30,3
2	30 - 39 Years	34	34,3

2	40 – 49 Years	25	25,3
3	≥ 50 Years	10	10,1
Total		99	100

The majority of respondents were of productive age (30–39 years), which indicates that policy implementers are dominated by age groups with relatively mature work experience and decision-making capacity.

Table 2 Respondent Characteristics Based on Gender.

No.	Gender	n	%
1	man	38	38,4
2	Woman	61	61,6
Total		99	100

Female respondents outnumbered male respondents. This reflects the institutional characteristics of the DP3APPKB, which substantially involves more women in women and child protection services.

Table 3 Respondent Characteristics Based on Education.

No.	Education	n	%
1	SMA/ SMK	21	21,2
2	Diploma III	23	23,2
3	Bachelor degree	45	45,5
4	Postgraduate (S2/S3)	10	10,1
Total		99	100

Most respondents had undergraduate (S1) and postgraduate degrees, which indicates that policy implementers have adequate academic capacity to understand regulations, SOPs, and the complexities of handling sexual violence.

3.3 Univariate Analysis of Research Variables

Table 4 Distribution of Communication Variables

No.	communication	n	%
1	Not good	21	21,2
2	Good	78	78,8
Total		99	100

Most respondents rated communication as good (78.8%), which indicates that in general the flow of information, coordination, and policy delivery has been running relatively optimally.

Table 5 Distribution of Resource Variables

No.	Resource	n	%
1	Not good	18	18,2
2	good	81	81,8
Total		99	100

81.8% of respondents stated that resources were in a good category. However, limitations remain in certain areas, such as budget and service facilities.

Table 6 Distribution of Disposition Variables (Implementer Attitudes)

No.	Disposition (Attitude of the Implementer)	n	%
1	Not good	24	24,2
2	good	75	75,8
Total		99	100

The majority of respondents assessed the disposition of the implementers as good, demonstrating commitment, empathy, and integrity in providing services to victims.

Table 7 Distribution of Bureaucratic Structure Variables

No.	Bureaucratic Structure	n	%
1	Not good	12	12,1
2	good	87	87,9
Total		99	100

The bureaucratic structure was assessed as good by almost all respondents, indicating that SOPs, division of tasks, and coordination mechanisms were available and relatively clear.

Table 8 Distribution of Patriarchal Cultural Variables

No.	Patriarchal Culture	n	%
1	Not good	20	20,2
2	Good	79	79,8
Total		99	100

Although the majority of respondents considered patriarchal culture to be good, there is still the influence of patriarchal values that have the potential to hinder the reporting and handling of cases.

Table 9 Distribution of Policy Implementation Effectiveness

No.	Implementation Effectiveness	n	%
1	Less Effective	20	20,2
2	Effective	79	79,8
Total		99	100

As many as 79.8% of respondents assessed that the implementation of the policy for handling sexual violence was effective, but there was still room for improvement, especially in the aspects of sustainability and equitable distribution of services.

3.4 Bivariate Analysis

Table 10 The Influence of Communication on the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

Communication	Effectiveness of Policy Implementation				Total		Statistical Value
	Not enough		effective		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not enough	9	42,9	12	57,1	21	100	$\alpha = 0,004$ $\rho = 0,293$
Good	11	14,1	67	85,9	78	100	
Total	20	20,2	79	79,8	99	100	

Statistical tests showed a p-value of 0.004, indicating that communication significantly influences the effectiveness of policy implementation. Good communication improves cross-sector coordination and service delivery accuracy.

Table 11 The Influence of Resources on the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

Resource	Effectiveness of Policy Implementation				Total		Statistical Value
	Not enough		effective		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not enough	8	44,4	10	55,6	18	100	$\alpha = 0,005$ $\rho = 0,285$
Good	12	14,8	69	85,2	81	100	
Total	20	20,2	79	79,8	99	100	

A p-value of 0.005 indicates that resources have a significant influence. The availability of human resources, budget, and facilities determines the sustainability of victim services.

Table 12 The Influence of Disposition on the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

Disposition (Attitude of the Implementer)	Effectiveness of Policy Implementation				Total		Statistical Value
	Not enough		Effective		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not enough	9	37,5	15	62,5	24	100	$\alpha = 0,015$ $\rho = 0,244$
Good	11	14,7	64	85,3	75	100	
Total	20	20,2	79	79,8	99	100	

The disposition of the implementer had a significant influence (p-value = 0.015). Empathetic and responsive attitudes were shown to improve service quality and victim trust.

Table 13 The Influence of Bureaucratic Structure on the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

Bureaucratic Structure	Effectiveness of Policy Implementation				Total		Statistical Value
	Not enough		Effective		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not enough	6	50,0	6	50,0	12	100	$\alpha = 0,006$ $\rho = 0,276$
Good	14	16,1	73	83,9	87	100	

Total	20	20,2	79	79,8	99	100
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Bureaucratic structure has a significant influence (p -value = 0.006). Clear SOPs and structured coordination support policy effectiveness.

Table 14 The Influence of Patriarchal Culture on the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

Patriarchal Culture	Effectiveness of Policy Implementation				Total		Statistical Value
	Not enough		Effective		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not enough	8	40,0	12	60,0	20	100	$\alpha = 0,014$ $\rho = 0,248$
Good	12	15,2	67	84,8	79	100	
Total	20	20,2	79	79,8	99	100	

Patriarchal culture had a significant influence (p -value = 0.014), although its strength was lower than other variables. Patriarchal values still influence the attitudes of society and authorities toward victims. Analisis Multivariat

Table 15 Multivariate Candidate Variables

variables	P value
communication	0,002
resource	0,026
Disposition (Attitude of the Implementer)	0,004
Bureaucratic Structure	0,033
Patriarchal Culture	0,088

Based on Table 4.15, the variables of communication, resources, disposition, bureaucratic structure, and patriarchal culture meet the requirements for further analysis in a multivariate logistic regression model.

Table 16 First Multivariate Modeling

Variables	B	P value	Exp B	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
communication	-2,261	0,002	0,104	0,025	0,431
resource	-1,669	0,026	0,188	0,043	0,818
Disposition (Attitude of the Implementer)	-2.146	0,004	0,117	0,027	0,508
Bureaucratic Structure	-1,731	0,033	0,177	0,036	0,869
Budaya Patriarki	-1,217	0,088	0,296	0,073	1,199

Based on Table 4.16, the patriarchal culture variable has the largest p -value (0.088) and is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), so it is removed from the model in the next stage.

Table 17 Second Multivariate Modeling

Variables	B	P value	Exp B	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
communication	-2,247	0,001	0,106	0,027	0,416
resource	-1,854	0,011	0,157	0,037	0,656
Disposition (Attitude of the Implementer	-2,099	0,003	0,123	0,030	0,496
Bureaucratic Structure	-1,849	0,025	0,157	0,031	0,796

The final multivariate modeling results indicate that communication, resources, implementer disposition, and bureaucratic structure significantly influence the effectiveness of policy implementation for addressing sexual violence against women and children. Among all independent variables, resources have the most dominant influence, as indicated by the largest Odds Ratio (OR) value. This indicates that the availability and quality of resources significantly increase the likelihood of effective policy implementation. Therefore, resources are a key determinant of the successful implementation of policies for addressing sexual violence against women and children.

4. Discussion

4.1 The Influence of Communication on the Effectiveness of Implementation of Policies for Handling Sexual Violence against Women and Children

The results of the study indicate that communication significantly influences the effectiveness of policy implementation for addressing sexual violence against women and children ($p = 0.004$). Respondents with good communication predominantly rated policy implementation as more effective than those with poor communication, indicating that clear instructions, consistent information, cross-sector coordination, and public information transparency play a crucial role in ensuring optimal policy implementation. This finding aligns with Edward III's (1980) theory, which positions communication as a key variable in policy implementation. It is also supported by research by Putri and Pratiwi (2021), Wulandari et al. (2022), and Rasyid (2023), which emphasizes that clear and coordinated communication improves the quality of victim services. Internationally, Arenas and Holden (2024) and UN Women (2025) emphasize that a strong cross-agency communication system accelerates responses and increases the effectiveness of policies addressing gender-based violence.

4.2 The Influence of Resources on the Effectiveness of Implementation of Policies for Handling Sexual Violence against Women and Children

Resources were shown to have a significant relationship with the effectiveness of sexual violence policy implementation ($p = 0.005$), with respondents with better resources largely rating policy implementation as more effective. This finding suggests that the availability of competent human resources, adequate budgets, service facilities, and technical skills are key prerequisites for policy success. This study's findings align with the theories of Edward III (1980) and Van Meter and Van Horn (1975), which assert that without sufficient resources, policies cannot be implemented optimally. Empirical support is also provided by Rahmawati and Idris (2021), Sitorus (2022), Nababan et al. (2023), and a UN Women report (2024), which concluded that strengthening resources directly improves the effectiveness of women's and children's protection services.

4.3 The Influence of Implementer Disposition on the Effectiveness of Implementation of Policies for Handling Sexual Violence against Women and Children

Implementer disposition significantly influenced the effectiveness of policy implementation ($p = 0.015$), where responsiveness, integrity, consistency in implementing SOPs, and empathy toward victims improved service quality and policy success. This finding confirms that policies depend not only on structure and resources, but also on the value orientation and commitment of implementers in the field. These results align with Edward III's (1980) theory, which places disposition as a central variable in implementation. This finding is supported by research by Ambarwati (2021), Sumirat and Widodo (2022), and Lee and Park (2024), which shows that implementer empathy and integrity are key determinants of victim trust and the effectiveness of sexual violence management.

4.4 The Influence of Bureaucratic Structure on the Effectiveness of Implementation of Policies for Handling Sexual Violence against Women and Children

Bureaucratic structure has a significant relationship with the effectiveness of policy implementation ($p = 0.006$), although the strength of the relationship is relatively low, indicating that policy effectiveness is not solely determined by the existence of SOPs and the formal division of authority. This finding indicates that bureaucratic flexibility, actor capacity, and cross-sector coordination can compensate for the weaknesses of the formal structure. This finding is in line with the theories of Edward III (1980) and Van Meter and Van Horn (1975), and is supported by research by Sari and Rahmawati (2022), Wijaya (2023), and Lestari et al. (2024), which confirm that adaptive bureaucracy is more effective in handling urgent and complex cases of sexual violence.

4.5 The Influence of Patriarchal Culture on the Effectiveness of Implementing Policies for Handling Sexual Violence against Women and Children

Patriarchal culture was shown to significantly influence the effectiveness of sexual violence policy implementation ($p = 0.014$), where gender stereotypes, resistance to equality, justification of violence, and discrimination against victims became cultural barriers to policy implementation. This finding suggests that a normatively sound policy can be ineffective if patriarchal values persist in the mindset of implementers. The results of this study align with the findings of Nursyahbani (2022), Rahayu et al. (2023), Sadiq and Hassan (2024), and Williams and Chen (2025), who emphasized that organizational culture reform and strengthening gender perspectives are key prerequisites for successful sexual violence policies.

4.6 Most Dominant Factors Influencing the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

The results of the multivariate analysis indicate that resources are the most dominant factor influencing the effectiveness of policy implementation, as indicated by the highest Odds Ratio (OR) value compared to other variables. This finding indicates that institutions with competent human resources, adequate budgets, comprehensive service facilities, and strong technical skills have a much greater chance of implementing policies effectively. This finding aligns with the theory of Edward III (1980) and is supported by Fitriani and Handayani (2021), Sari et al. (2022), WHO (2021), and UN Women (2024), which emphasize that strengthening resources is the main foundation for the success of women's and children's protection policies.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results and discussion, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of the implementation of policies for handling sexual violence against women and children at the Office of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning (DP3APPKB) of Southeast Sulawesi Province is significantly influenced by communication factors, resources, implementer disposition, bureaucratic structure, and patriarchal culture. Clear and coordinated communication, the availability of adequate resources, and responsive and empathetic implementer dispositions have been shown to improve the quality and effectiveness of policy services. In addition, a supportive bureaucratic structure and the low influence of patriarchal culture play a significant role in facilitating the policy implementation process. These findings indicate that the success of policies for handling sexual violence is determined not only by administrative aspects, but also by interrelated organizational and cultural factors. Thus, strengthening all of these factors simultaneously is a primary prerequisite for increasing the effectiveness of policies for protecting women and children in a sustainable manner.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author would like to express his sincere gratitude to the Faculty of Public Health, Postgraduate Program, Halu Oleo University, as well as to all individuals and institutions who have contributed to the completion of this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this research.

References

- [1] World Health Organization, *Violence Against Women Prevalence Estimates, 2018*, WHO/RHR/21.09. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/978924002225>
- [2] Kementerian Pemberdayaan Perempuan dan Perlindungan Anak (KemenPPPA), ""Continuous cross-sectoral and regional collaboration is the key to overcoming cases of violence against children." 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kemenpppa.go.id/page/view/NTAxNg>
- [3] J. Hos and Z. Larisu, "Factors causing violence against women in Kendari City," *Trajectories of Public Administration*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 81–94, 2025.
- [4] R. Nugroho, *Kebijakan Publik: Policy Implementation and Control*. Jakarta, Indonesia: Elex Media Komputindo, 2021.
- [5] J. Widodo, *Public Policy Analysis: Concepts and Applications of Public Policy Process Analysis*. Malang, Indonesia: Media Nusa Creative (MNC Publishing), 2021.
- [6] S. A. Wahab, *Policy Analysis: From Formulation to Developing Public Policy Implementation Models*. Jakarta, Indonesia: Bumi Aksara, 2021.
- [7] A. Jannah, M. Nazaruddin, and D. A. Rahman, "Implementation of Aceh Qanun Number 9 of 2019 concerning the implementation of handling violence against women and children," *Public Transparency Journal (JTP)*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 10–18, 2022.
- [8] S. W. K. Sutopo and I. D. A. Nurhaeni, "Implementation of the provision of protection for women and children who are victims of domestic violence in Magetan Regency," *Public Discourse Student Journal*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 52–72, 2024.
- [9] A. F. Sari and L. E. Retnaningsih, *Understanding Violence Against Children and Women*. Jakarta, Indonesia: PT Adab Indonesia, 2024.
- [10] D. T. Todapa and J. Juemi, "Implementation of policies for handling acts of violence against women at the Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service of Palu City," *Jurnal Ilmiah Nusantara*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 94–104, 2024.
- [11] L. Maghfiroh, S. Suyeno, and L. R. Putra, "Implementation of domestic violence handling policies (study at the integrated service center for the protection of women and children in Batu City)," *Public Response*, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 55–64, 2022.
- [12] L. J. Bacchus et al., "Interventions that prevent or respond to intimate partner violence against women and violence against children: A systematic review," *The Lancet Public Health*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. e326–e338, 2024.
- [13] R. M. Olson, C. Garcia-Moreno, and M. Colombini, "The implementation and effectiveness of the one stop centre model for intimate partner and sexual violence in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review of barriers and enablers," *BMJ Global Health*, vol. 5, no. 3, 2020.